

A group of people, including children and adults, are gathered on a sandy beach looking out at the ocean. In the middle ground, a person is standing on a small raft made of logs, holding a long pole. The water is a clear blue, and the sky is overcast with grey clouds. In the background, there are low, rocky islands or peninsulas.

Creative Learning Environment

Discovering New Educational Horizons from a small Island

Research Report
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*Imagination
is more important
than knowledge. For
knowledge is limited
to all we now know
and understand, while
imagination embraces the
entire world, and all there
ever will be to know and
understand.*

Albert Einstein

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Index

Preface - Purpose of This Report _____	02
Part 1	
Creative Learning Environment	
Why Do We Need A Different Learning Environment? _____	03
Exploring The World with All Our Senses _____	05
Okinawa Environment _____	10
Project Work and Immersive Curricula _____	11
Part 2	
Creative Learning Environment Model Projects _____	12
Project Space School - Immersing in Doing _____	13
House Project _____	14
Boat Project _____	18
Making Chairs and Other Objects _____	24
Project Space Community - Immersing in Society _____	25
Barbie in Sakaemachi Market _____	26
Exhibitions in Sakaemachi _____	30
Project Space Nature - Immersing in Nature _____	33
Shizen ni de kara: Exploring Water _____	34
Shizen ni de kara: Exploring Plants _____	40
Shizen ni de kara: Natural Playgrounds _____	42
Appendix	
Bibliography _____	46

This report provides a documentation and review of a number of projects that were realized as part of "Okinawa Alternative School" (short OAS), an alternative education project located in Japan's most southernmost prefecture Okinawa.

Founded by parents, teachers and supporters in 2009, the OAS initially offered a comprehensive elementary level school curriculum loosely based on the public school curriculum, but in 2012 this was restructured toward an emphasis on extra curricular weekend activities for children that attend normal public or private schools.

This report covers both phases of the OAS activity but focuses on that part of the curriculum that can be summarized as project studies and therefore leaves out the normal class room lessons which made up roughly half of the curriculum in terms of weekly hours.

It is a characteristic of the OAS to combine a global and contemporary educational knowledge base with locally rooted experience of the Okinawan environment.

From the outset the educational vision has been to create a child-oriented open and cooperative learning environment in which the process of learning would be immersed in Okinawa's natural and social context, so that children could enjoy a comprehensive learning experience that not only challenges their intellect but involves the whole personality and supports them in their natural striving to embark on the adventure it means to explore this world full of wonders on their own.

This report shows the sometimes difficult reality of a creative approach toward this kind of learning.

With this report I introduce an educational approach and a number of projects that exemplify the approach. The projects shown were realized over the course of more than 4 years starting in 2009, but in terms of educational research the work has just began and therefore this report should not be taken as a finished research paper but rather as an illustrated preview of what is possible and can be expected from such an environment focused approach toward learning.

What I present here is not only research about "learning by doing", but in itself "learning by doing" (= "researching by doing"). My approach is not so much based on a theoretical analysis of educational theories but reflects a rather intuitive curriculum and program design that has taken shape in an intense dialogue with the Okinawan environment and with friends and collaborators but also grown through the even more intense interaction with the children who have been the main actors here.

Rather than a manual this report is meant to be a source of inspiration for how to incorporate various kinds of environments into the process of learning and teaching intended for researchers, educational practitioners, decision makers, parents and interested laypeople.

While schools and educational institutions are more and more under competitive pressure to satisfy claims that are globally defined by achievement test scores that express only a small part of the students abilities, learning as suggested here means to set off on an adventurous journey of which we don't know where exactly it will lead us. An adventure that involves us in our entirety and with all our senses.

This approach has been possible only thanks to the restless effort and dedication of all involved individuals and is therefore not a model for "normal" institutionalized learning, but it nevertheless shows what is possible if we are able to organize learning in a different way.

In this chapter I will discuss some of the considerations that led to the foundation of the Okinawa Alternative School (OAS) and the Creative Learning Environment projects.

To me the institution called school has always been a mystery. Why are we supposed to sit with 30 or so same aged pupils in a class room, listen to a teacher, read, write, think, sometimes talk and be bored for a good part of the time in order to prepare for life? How did we get to this incredibly narrow and static model of learning, when it is clear that we will later embark on a rather diverse journey through life that will require a variety of different skills and experiences? When and where did this start? And most importantly, is there no alternative?

I'm surely not the first one to ask such questions, and it would go beyond the scope of this report to provide a balanced and in-depth answer, but since these questions stood at the beginning of this research and the activities of the Okinawa Alternative School (OAS) that I am documenting here, I would like to at least briefly touch on them in order to prepare the ground for the different notion of school I am presenting.

Not having done any formal research into the topic, it is intuition that tells me that the reason for institutionalized education being what it is has more to do with "institution" than with "education". Besides education for the masses - something that important educational pioneers such as Pestalozzi and Humboldt laudably aspired to - and the related need to develop a manageable system of education on a national level, we can see the necessities of rapid growth as well as business and industry's demand for a "usable" workforce as formative influences on modern institutionalized education. During this development the question of what is manageable seems to have been given more attention than the question of how learning ought to happen.

From the outset of the institutionalization of education at the beginning of our democratic nations in the 18th and 19th century we can observe a growing tension between the management of the educational system, a bureaucracy far away from the learning

locations, and the practitioners, i.e. the educators, who are right in the middle of it. The ongoing crisis of the educational systems in almost all modern states is in my view the direct result of a clash between the viewpoint of the managers, who think in terms of functionality, rationalization and feasibility, and the viewpoint of the educators, who have to make sure that their students learn their lessons despite the tough targets set by the managers.

It is no accident that the early models for institutionalized teaching were based on procedures borrowed from the military, as there was no way to convey a precast, rationalized curriculum to a bustling horde of children, who, by natural inclination and their experience of a world that was by far less organized and institutionalized than today's world, were more up to all kinds of fun than to sitting on chairs for long hours every day.

But humans are incredibly adaptable, and this is especially true for adapting to social circumstances, however odd they may be. We've got used to institutionalized education, and I don't want to deny that it had some positive results, such as raising literacy rates and making society work, but I am sure there are feasible alternatives if the educational vision is clear enough.

Since the early days of institutionalized learning a number of gifted education reformers with a strong vision have tried to reshape the system, but despite various changes to the curriculum and the teaching methods, the overall shape of the institution "school" has largely remained the same, and its connections to society and nature are at best weak, if they exist at all. It is interesting to note that the biggest stimuli for reform have come from outside of the formal system and were mostly developed in alternative educational settings and only later and to some part incorporated into mainstream educational policies.

Still, the learner is more than anything else defined by a chair in a class room and occupies a place in the physical framework of a school building and in the charts of the institution "school". Except for a few field trips the experience of the learner is thus confined to a more or less well designed box. The only learning environment we have are the school premises and anything that happens outside of

that environment is not the responsibility of the educational institution and therefore not related to the curriculum. With what justification do we say that school prepare young people for life?

In my view, this autistic seclusion from real life and acquiescence to bureaucratic presets are the main reasons why institutionalized learning is as inefficient as it is.

In this report I would like to introduce an experimental approach toward a school curriculum that, for the lack of a shorter and catchier name, I will call „Creative Learning Environment“. It relies on the theoretical side on a definition of “learning” and “environment” that challenges the typical notions of “education” and “school” and on the practical side on certain educational projects that were realized in Okinawa. That is to say, learning is not defined by a content set that can be conveyed in a written manual or by way of lectures but as activities that immerse the learners in their environment with all their senses. And that environment is not limited to a classroom but includes the natural world and society at large.

The need for educational reform, especially toward education that involves the learning environment, was already recognized at the beginning of the era of institutionalized education. Educational pioneers like Steiner and Montessori carefully integrated the topic into their educational approach. Especially Montessori, who believed that sensorial education in the classroom is extremely important, developed a style of learning that focuses on classroom design and enriches the learning environment with a plethora of tools to provide children with a sensorially satisfying learning experience.

Although an immersed and sensorial way of learning can in this way be realized to some extent even in an institutionalized learning environment, the Creative Learning Environment approach suggests that exposure to a multiplicity of environments, natural and social, inspires learners in a way that no controlled or well designed classroom environment ever could.

The key feature of the Creative Learning Environment approach is to involve children through various kinds of project work in different real world environments, and this is not difficult to implement in an

alternative school setting, as we have been able to demonstrate at the OAS, but it appears unlikely that the educational system in Japan as it currently exists would be able to make use of it.

The illustration below provides a simple representation of Creative Learning Environment as practiced in the OAS where we have defined three interconnected learning environments: school, nature and community.

The three overlapping activity fields school, nature and community form the Creative Learning Environment developed at OAS. While a major part of the curriculum has been taking place in a traditional classroom setting, the part documented here extends beyond the borders of the schoolyard into Okinawa's natural and social environment.

Projects of various forms become the curricular tool - together with traditional classroom lessons - to immerse the learners in various environments and let them become active and independent participants in an open process of acquiring knowledge and experience.

One of the central considerations of the Creative Learning Environment approach is the holistic involvement of our entire sensorial body in the process of learning. In this chapter I want to introduce some of the central thoughts behind this immersive, creative and sensory rich educational practice.

To understand the world around us we have our senses. We start our exploration of the world as fetuses in the womb, sensing the heart beat of our mother, the reverberation of her voice, feeling the rhythm of her movements. By the time we are born we know more about our mother than any collection of objectified knowledge could ever provide us with.

We have so to say embodied her features and stored an image of her in our biological self that is not visual and not objectifiable but nevertheless a precise representation of our sensorial experience, and after we are born we continue to integrate what we perceive of the world around us in much the same way.

Besides our genetic code the mother image is the first of many imprints that will make us to who we are and will define the basis of our character. From recent research we know how strongly a pregnant woman's experiences and moods affect the wellbeing of her unborn child, and it is clear that this is largely due to the sensorial experience of the unborn.

Perceiving the world is one of the most basic programs that is built into us. Our growing into this world is accompanied by a plethora of sensations and by a constant reconfirmation, by way of our senses, that we are physical beings and that our movements in this world are not mere projections. In early childhood we literally absorb the world around us and our senses are more receptive than they will ever be later in our life. But even when we grow older the sensorial being in us is always there and creates the base for our interaction with the world.

Unfortunately for the large part this exploring the world with all our senses is absent in the modern day school curriculum, save for some very few hands on experiments and special projects. The overwhelming part of our learning experience in school is restricted to a readily comprehensible environment and focused on very limited

sensorial input related to largely intellectual subjects.

In school we actually learn quite well to shut down a major part of our senses and to focus on a very narrowed down interaction with the school environment in order to be able to fulfill the requirements of the curriculum that is meant to “fill us” with precast knowledge about the world. It seems we humans are stunningly adaptable animals, since we adjust to this brain centered learning and store endless data and fragmented information somewhere in our neurons so that we are able to recall some of it in order to succeed in various forms of examinations. But what happens after the exam? Many people wonder how all that stored “knowledge” disappears after we finish institutionalized education. I don't know of any conclusive research into this matter, but I suspect that our brain has developed quite efficient means of getting rid of large chunks of unused and unusable data as soon as the related tasks are completed.

But recent research, in particular that in the field of *embodied cognition*, suggests that rich sensorial input at the time we learn something, be it intellectual or practical, can make what we learn much more versatile and more deeply rooted in our memory.

Judging from such emerging research and the OAS experience I believe a future oriented educational institution must offer a multifaceted learning environment with rich sensorial input and a curriculum that involves different experiences in different contexts. Traditional institutions that rely on a clearly defined and managed environment, which limits the perception of the learners to a usually well organized space that does not invite deeper exploration and does not provide many unforeseen experiences, results in a rather shallow learning experience and fragmented information that is not sustainable in memory.

Even though many teachers know that it is important to experience different environments, the manner in which education is structured and the related educational policies make it incredibly difficult to set up a curriculum that regularly includes the world beyond the premises of the school. As we know from the very few school excursions our children participated in, leaving the school is always a stressful affair for the teachers whose main job it is to keep their students safe, but as recent research suggests, keeping children always in safe environments means they do not learn how the world really works and consequently end up suffering serious injuries. Schools as they currently exist are for many reasons not in a position to encourage an exploration of the world with all one's senses, but learning and exploring are siblings and there is a small explorer in each of us who strives to learn about the world we live in, to experience things first hand and to *get in touch* with reality.

The role of the teachers in the OAS context is quite different from the traditional notion of teacher. Of course they need to take care of children's safety, but it is not their job to convey a precast body of knowledge - they are facilitators, opening doors through which the students can step and start their own explorations.

This exploration involves all senses and is not restricted to a protected environment - per Montessori - but extends into the real world. In order to understand the complex interdependencies of our natural and social environment, students need to move around, take various standpoints / points of view (both physically and figuratively), and get a feeling for things and situations - this is an essential holistic activity leading to experience that no purely intellectual knowledge can make up for.

The projects at the OAS represent a variety of approaches to exploration and sensorial interaction with various environments but share common

ground in that they all involve the children in a way that they are immersed in both the process of learning and the environment they deal with.

Hands on Learning

Our hands are without doubt the most active parts of our sensorial body. They are not a sense per se, but they are a versatile tool to extend our sense of touch into the surrounding space and proactively explore ("grasp") the world and to manage ("handle") it.

But our hands are more than that, they are the most human of all body features and have contributed to our evolution, especially that of the

OAS learning cycle

During the project work at OAS a kind of learning routine gained a foothold that involved the same components in different compositions: experience, experiment, express, discuss and play. In the usual school curricula we are mostly confronted with a very one dimensional process of learning that is confined by the school environment and the curriculum made for such an institution, but if it is possible to explore a wider environment by a longer term project studies approach, a much more multifaceted form of learning like shown here becomes possible.

brain, more than any other part of the body. As Frank R. Wilson convincingly describes in his groundbreaking book "The Hand", the evolution of the human brain and of human culture would not have been possible without the direct involvement of the hand. In particular Wilson introduces a number of people for whom the ability to use their hands in special and skilled way has had an enormous and largely positive impact on the development of their personality and the course of their lives. He goes so far as to critically analyze the stunning absence of hand usage in modern school curricula. Wilson also links hand usage and creativity as he describes real-world examples where skillful development of the hand leads to a boost in creative energy.

Education Toward Creativity and Imagination

Creativity is an elusive quality, and that makes it so difficult to handle in the context of institutionalized education. Nevertheless it is becoming increasingly obvious that creativity is one of the essential "ingredients" of an education that brings about people who thrive as adults.

In 1958 Ellis Paul Torrance started a long term test series with elementary school children in Minnesota that focused on creativity. Over the course of more than 40 years the research showed in a stunning way how much more than intelligence scores lifetime achievements were determined by creativity scores. The most astonishing part of this research was the fact that Torrance's creativity scores of elementary school children would quite exactly predict the creative accomplishments of those kids once they grew up. Kids who came up with more good ideas on Torrance's test would later become entrepreneurs, inventors, college presidents, authors, doctors, diplomats, and software developers.

Being creative and inventive is without doubt one of the inherent human qualities we are born with, but education can have a huge influence on how this quality develops and whether it will prevail in our adult life.

How to foster creativity and imagination is one of the most difficult questions in educational theory and practice. It is so difficult because by virtue creativity and imagination cannot be squeezed into any kind of precast curriculum. We can usually see clearly when someone is creative, but as soon as we try to analyze where exactly a creative impetus comes from or how exactly it works we are facing a kind of enigma. Currently it is not yet well understood what fosters creativity, but to me it seems clear that an environment that offers a rich sensorial experience, like, for example, the natural environment, can do a lot to inspire children to be creative. Observing how a small child is immersed in a natural environment, mesmerized by the beauty and multiplicity of sensations, animatedly playing with leaves, flowers, insects or other found objects, can make us realize how creativity is linked to perception and stimulating sensorial experience.

Expressing ourselves in various ways while using different tools can make creativity flow. Creativity needs form in order to develop and there are numerous forms it can take, like the different genres in art or writing or performance. Creativity develops in the form of dialogue, whether it is an inner dialogue with or without words, or a dialogue with peers.

The projects I introduce in this documentation are not to be seen as clear explanation of how one should foster creativity, but they all were experiments that led to varying degrees of creative activity on part of the participating children, sometimes in quite astonishing ways.

Understanding through Expression and Dialogue

Artistic representation of what we see is one of the starting points of modern science, even though this has not been acknowledged much until recently. The great explorers and scientific travelers of the 18th and 19th century, such as James Cook and Alexander von Humboldt, the pioneering botanists, biologists and zoologist like Carl Linnaeus, Jean-Henri Fabre and Ernst Haeckel, all these explorers of the real world have to a large extent based their contributions to science on astonishing drawings that go far beyond the exact "scientific" representation of a visible reality and instead incorporate, to varying degrees, a visual analysis on part of the observers.

In order to represent a complex reality visually we have to get beyond the first impression and analyze an object in such a way that we are able to transfer it to a specific style of visual representation that is defined by our ability and its limits as well as by the tools we have at our disposal. This is a form of abstraction very different from the one we know from objective science, but one very common to the world of artistic expression.

We have manifold channels to explore and understand what we see and we should also have manifold modes of representation and analysis, but in the "normal" school curriculum the way we look at reality is largely dominated by a very specific form of representation that in visual and perceptual terms is much

poorer than what was available at the beginning of the scientific revolution, a time when there was much less distance between art and natural sciences. One of the main tasks of the experimental approach toward environmental education introduced here was to link various modes of creative expression to scientific observation of nature and environment. The act of expressing an individual observation in a creative way means not only to represent reality, but also to recreate it with one's own means, and this is in many respects very similar to the act of teaching, since we have to really permeate whatever we want to convey to others. Moreover, expression is the foundation of communication and dialogue with others. While verbal expression is a natural feature of dialogue it is interesting to see how visual expression can foster the ability to communicate and actually have positive effect on language development.

Open and non-goal-directed dialogue plays in the OAS curriculum. Many of the projects introduced here start with dialogue and take their respective shape through an intensive communication process. While immersion in the environment often requires a certain quietness and seclusion, dialogue is a different kind of immersion where we start to reflect on our experiences. In the OAS context, dialogue is a part of all the stages of a project, from the initial idea development and research, through the implementation that involves interacting with people in a social context (for example, in a market), to the reflection at the end, after a project has been completed.

Okinawa's Environment

With Okinawa offering a unique and multifaceted environment the question: „What would an ideal school curriculum for Okinawa look like if we could develop it from the ground up and without the restraints of the Japanese education system?“ has followed me since I moved to Okinawa and started thinking about education.

I felt from the beginning that this island in many ways is an ideal place to think about education and to raise children. By ideal I not only mean a positive environment, which it surely is, but also that it is a place where conflicts and tasks that human society faces are quite apparent.

When starting to develop a curriculum for our newly founded OAS it was important to ensure that our kids would become a part of Okinawa's inspiring natural and social environment. Okinawa's natural context is dominated by the sea and by the natural forces that a small piece of land in a huge ocean experiences directly. It is a rather readily comprehensible micro cosmos, even though it is of course interrelated with a huge natural system.

Living on an island like Okinawa creates a sense of being framed and restrained, but this can also make it easier to see the big picture of nature.

Okinawa's human context is defined by closeness and intimacy which seems to make people attentive and sensitive for things human. At the same time, other than in Japan, there is a culture of generosity toward individuality and diversity of the human character. I feel this praise of the individual goes so far that I sometimes get the impression Okinawa is an archipelago full of artists, though of course not professional ones.

A SELECTION OF LOCATIONS ON OKINAWA ISLAND THAT WERE PART OF OUR OAS IMMERSIVE CURRICULUM

Project Work and Immersive Curricula

The concept of project studies by now is well known in the educational world and there is a wide array of literature and methods covering the topic. Educational reformers like Calvin M. Woodward, William H. Kilpatrick and John Dewey have introduced the idea of project work into the modern school curriculum, but even though it has become a commodity in educational theory it has never really managed to gain traction, largely due to the requirements and limitations put up by the educational bureaucracy. Project work is difficult to control and hard to evaluate with exact scores and therefore does not play much of a role in modern school curricula. There are few, usually experimental, schools where project studies thrive, but they tend to be organized independently from the educational bureaucracy.

Other than in big schools a small organization with fewer pupils like the OAS downright invites the project approach. In the OAS curriculum projects play a central role, but of course also in combination with normal class room lessons.

Our curriculum is an example for how to integrate these two seemingly opposite modes of learning. The weekly schedule is split into more traditional class room activity, which includes concentrated and incremental language and math lessons, and project days, when learning is organized around longer term tasks and usually takes place moving around in various locations.

The illustration of the OAS model curriculum shows how the weekly schedule is divided into normal class room lessons and project work that takes place in different location and with different teachers. The schedule features both worlds, the objective-analytical approach and sensorial-immersive approach.

Okinawa Alternative School Model Curriculum

	monday	tuesday	wednesday	thursday	friday	
8:45	Class room	Class room	Nature/Class room	Class room	Class room	Class time
	Japanese Math	Japanese Math	place: Nature and Environmental Study Center Naha	Japanese Math	Japanese Math	
	poetrie review	review sports	Biology, Environmental education	review sports	review	
				School meeting		
12:30	Cooking together Lunch break	Lunch break	Lunch break	Lunch break	Lunch break	
13:30	Project studies Kids Yoga, Gymnastics	Project studies Arts and Crafts	Project studies Playing in Nature, Building and Constructing	Project studies Music	Project studies English	Project time
15:30						

The projects described on the following pages are a selection that represents a form of organizing learning that I would like to call "Immersive Curriculum". This involves mainly two parts, a project and a field, or in other word a task and a location. Sometimes the project is more at the center of attention, sometimes the location, but in all cases it is the interdependency of both that makes for a rich and multifaceted learning experience that involves the learner in his or her entirety. It is an approach comparable to the Montessori class room, just that it extends the field out of the protected institution into the "real world".

Part 2 Creative Learning Environment Model Projects

In order to show in a concrete context what I mean by Creative Learning Environment I will introduce a selection of projects that were part of the OAS curriculum in the second part of this report. As the projects were realized over a period of four years they span a wide range of themes and environments. They are not shown in chronological order, but are roughly grouped according to the three experience fields mentioned earlier: school, community and nature.

The separation is not in every respect consistent, as it is a characteristic of the OAS projects to cross borders and connect different fields of experience like it happens in the real world, but rather a weighting of where the main part of the project takes place. For example the Boat project was mainly constructed in the school space in is therefor classified under school, but also connects very directly to Okinawas natural environment as the final event, the launching of the boats happened at the beach. There also is a variety of forms that the projects take, as their role within the curriculum can be quite different. Some of the projects were accomplished in 3 month and ended with a proper exhibition whereas others span over two or more years and involved different groups of children in a successive process.

Approach to the OAS

The current location and environment of the OAS is quite unique: an almost isolated small house set in-between fields and green space, but just a ten minute walk from the Monorail station and the castle of the Ryukyuan kings in Shuri (now incorporated into the city of Naha, the capitol of Okinawa Prefecture).

The unfinished character of the place was one of the reasons that we decided to rent the building, since it would give children an opportunity to be involved in the creation of their school environment. From the outset OAS pupils were directly and actively involved in all decisions concerning the usage and the refinement of the school hardware. This is of course an experience a normal school institution can hardly provide, given the fact that large numbers of pupils use various spaces in terms, but it turned out to be one of the most interesting experiences in terms of learning environment.

Similar to the adventure playgrounds or building playgrounds that are common in many cities in Europe and the US, the imperfectness of the OAS environment invites the user to be active and to change things. There are a large number of tools and part of the school space is dedicated to all kind of manual work.

The following projects are just a small selection of the activities that took place in the OAS space since its inauguration in July 2011, but they can give an idea about what a different kind of school environment and handwork in a school curriculum can look like.

OAS space layout

The house project was carried out in several stages from December 2011 to September 2013 on the premises of the OAS.

To build a house is not something that one would usually consider part of a normal children's experience, but it is without doubt an incredibly fascinating task for them.

In general kids love to engage in projects that seem too big to handle and rarely back off if told how hard the work might be. Of course they might start to back off if things get really tedious, but it is quite astonishing to see how far they are willing to go if they set their goals themselves.

Over the course of 2 years and with the restless participation of the OAS kids we constructed a small house in the OAS school yard. The house building activity was not planned like a traditional project with a beginning, a clear task and an end when the task is fulfilled, but rather it turned out to be like a succession of projects working on the same structure always picking up where the last activity had left off.

Reusing found materials, such as wood from a demolished traditional style Okinawan house, and simple construction methods, a wood structure rose and changed over and over again.

At the start of the project we looked at different architecture examples and drafted some ideas. As with all big construction work reality did pose some unforeseen problems, plans had to be adjusted and some of the tasks proved difficult or impossible for elementary age children, but they never gave up.

During the building process there were many different tasks that had to be carried out, like calculation, drawing, usage of various tools, advanced geometry, the hands on experience of different laws of physics and often children invented their very own way of doing things. For example at the beginning of the construction process, when measuring the wood pieces, they decided to give each main column and beam a different name, or developed their very own system of measurements by using their bodies as a measuring module.

The boat project was a part of the "Kodomo Kensetsubu", a regular Saturday class that I am responsible for at the OAS, and took place from January 19th, 2013 to March 29th, 2013

The idea to make a boat came up at a first meeting when we were discussing what we could do this time at the Kodomo Kensetsubu. The kids were immediately electrified by the idea, but I found it important to point out the challenges involved in such a project in order to get at least some kind of commitment from the group. After I had clearly described some of the tasks involved we decided that we would give it a try and not give up when facing obstacles.

The first step was to find out what the participants knew about boats and to discuss a project strategy. Of course 'project strategy' is not part of the vocabulary of elementary school children, but they soon had an idea what I was talking about. We agreed that we would not start with a big boat directly but to develop some ideas and build models first.

An extended literature and internet search gave us some ideas, and soon everybody was working on models. First we started with simple models from paper, later small wood models were created and extensively tested in our small school pond. Making a streamlined hull shape from wood at first seemed an almost unsolvable task, but with some research, intensive consultations and a lot of experiments the kids found several solutions to the problem.

For the actual construction of the boats the children chose to form two groups, each with a slightly different approach. This turned out to be a very stimulating mode of working as the two teams were challenging and inspiring each other.

For some reason both teams decided to construct trimarans, which didn't make things easier at all, but they managed to finish their boats by the end of the 3 month term. We launched the two wood trimarans and several smaller boats that were folded from a sheet of corrugated plastic from a beach in Sashiki, southern Okinawa.

First meeting and first model making. It is a quite challenging task to create a 3 dimensional boat hull from a sheet of paper or wood. Wood models were then launched in our small self-made school pond

All kinds of tools are quite intriguing for children and if allowed they like to try them all. While it looks dangerous we only had small scratches or bruises in our four plus years of project work with children

Through Tesuya Yasuda, a friend who is chairman of a sailing club and small ship building yard in the southern Okinawan harbor of Sashiki, we were able to visit a place where real boats are made.

The sailing club is located in a small harbor in southern Okinawa and there were a variety of different boats on site. Beside the usual sailing and cruising boats there also were a number of well preserved traditional style Okinawan boats called Sabani. The children were particularly interested in the wood construction of the Sabani, as they could establish a direct link with their own boat building efforts.

The excursion was not only inspiring because of the real world boats on site, but also because of Yasuda's short introduction into the history of seafaring in Okinawa. The children were able to understand how much the development of the Okinawan culture was relying on the ocean and on traveling by boat.

Boatman Tetsuya Yasuda talking about the traditional Okinawa Sabaani boat

Last preparations for the launch of the boats

Some of the educational concepts of the OAS boat and house projects

- no complete manuals (except for the ones found by the children themselves)
- mixed age groups in which participants learn with and from each other
- facing and solving problems together through dialogue
- involvement of all members in all decisions (as much as possible)
- showing how to do things rather than explaining
- failures along the way are the key to success

Learning Content

Building a proper boat or house requires a lot of knowledge and experience (skills). To mention some of the skills:

- dealing with a complex task
- planning a long term project
- looking for and finding information
- thinking about and researching materials
- experiencing and researching physical phenomena
- using a variety of tools
- dealing with complex, 3 dimensional forms
- using advanced geometry to make various shapes
- not giving up when facing seemingly adamant challenges
- using (and developing) appropriate language to discuss complex topics

Ship Ahoy!

After almost three month of intensive,
exhausting and sometimes frustrating work
the children thoroughly enjoy their boats.

Pure satisfaction!

Making chairs and other objects

During the Kodomo Kensetsubu activity children are free to make whatever they can imagine. Chairs, tables, toys, carts, animals and swords are just some of the objects that were created by the kids. It is a pleasure to observe the various forms of teamwork that emerge in such a free environment and the way children search for their role in a group. Experiments with making things in a group are always communication-rich experiences.

Over a period of 2 years the OAS was able to use a project space inside the "Sakaemachi market" in Naha, a traditional style market that features narrow alleys and many tiny market stalls. Being one of the few remaining markets in Okinawa, Sakaemachi is quite a special place with a unique atmosphere that appears to have more in common with south east Asian markets than with Japanese ones. We used the space mainly during the project study periods during the afternoon hours. Several of the projects realized there dealt directly with the market and had the children interact with the people working there, thus they were able to experience a variety of mindsets, occupations and ways to make business. The market and the marketeers became an important part of the the learning experience and the stage for a number of projects. At the end of each project period (usually after about 3 months) we set up an exhibition showing the works created by the children inside the market.

Barbie in Sakaemachi

A fashion, photography and exhibition project realized inside the Sakaemachi market as part of the afternoon project studies in June and July 2010

Being able to work with children in a traditional market is a quite unique experience, especially with marketeers so cheerful and cooperative as the ones in the Sakaemachi market. One of the projects we realized inside the market started as a fashion design assignment. The OAS kids were handed out a barbie and some felt and sewing tools to accouter the puppet. A small barbie fashion collection was created and we decided to use the market as our back ground and go on a fashion shooting tour in the small alleys of Sakaemachi. The market, built in the 1950s, features a unique environment with many small and very individual booths. While communicating with the merchants, and asking for permission, the children arranged their barbies in all kinds of possible and impossible locations. At some point marketeers started inviting us to use their booths as location for barbie fashion shooting.

The barbie, usually a well sheltered objects in a children's room became a tool for interaction and extended exploration of the market, but also an object that would change the scale of, and open up a complete new view on, a known environment. Eventually the children started developing stories around barbies tour through the market and the happenings at all those funny places she would appear.

Exhibitions in Sakaemachi

"Barbie in Sakaemachi" Exhibition

Juli 2010

Since the OAS project space in the Sakaemachi market was just a normal market booth, it was completely open to the market alleys and therefore open to the public. While this was not always ideal for creating a concentrated work atmosphere, and we often used curtains or screens for spacial seperation, it turned out to be a perfect place for public interaction, such as exhibitions or events.

Over the 2 year period that we were able to use the space we had 5 or 6 exhibitions and public events. The open space proved ideal for our community project curriculum, and the children became respected participants and contributors in the market community.

One of the main OAS events was a photo exhibition with the Barbie pictures and an improvised performance of the OAS kids.

"Minna no Tenjikai" Project and Exhibition

September to December 2009

The first exhibition that we held inside the Sakaemachi market was featuring objects made from beach glass during a 3 month project with the artist Kanako Yamazato. After collecting shards of glass and corals on a beach the children created illuminated artworks. The exhibition concept was developed together with the children and realized inside the OAS project space in Sakaemachi.

"Wool" Project and Exhibition

January to March 2010

The wool project was the second 3 month project realized inside the Sakaemachi market. The teacher Nahoko Kataoka used a specific wool craft technique in which a special needle is used to form balls and other shapes with wool. The children defined their own themes and created various objects as well as the exhibition design. Small thematic displays with the wool objects were arranged in the OAS exhibition space.

View of the the OAS project and exhibition space in the Sakaemachi market

Being in nature is an experience the “normal” school system simply cannot provide us with. Some greenery in the schoolyard, or a small biotope is all we can expect from a contemporary learning institute.

Just very recently the forest kindergarten has been gaining traction as a different kind of learning environment, but from the elementary

school level onward the idea of the closed class room setting is almost unchallenged.

Okinawa’s natural environment is rich and diverse as only few places on earth are. Although it accounts for less than 1% of the total land area of Japan, its rich subtropical natural environment features an equal if not higher variety of species than the rest of the country.

Our first concern when developing the OAS curriculum was to give children the opportunity to not only study nature but to immerse themselves in nature as long as possible. Through a collaboration with the “Mori no Ie Minmin” environmental education facility of the City of Naha we had the chance to work in the middle of one of the few remaining natural woods in the urban area.

“Shizen ni de kara”, which can roughly be translated as “In Nature, with Nature, from Nature, naturally” was the main OAS project dealing with the topic of Okinawa’s natural environment over a two year period. Partly funded by a research grant of the University of the Ryukyus

Shizen ni de kara played a central role in the OAS curriculum and integrated the fields of science education, environmental education, arts and crafts in a long term thematic study project with an exhibition at the end. During the first year of Shizen ni de kara the overarching theme was “water” and in the second year “plants”. With each theme spanning a one year period and each week one and a half days allotted to it, this long term curricular activity allowed children to gain an in depth understanding of a complex environmental topic.

Shizen ni de kara: Exploring Water

Exploring Water was the first section of the two year "Shizen ni de kara" project and took place from May 2010 to March 2011 mainly along the Aja river that flows from Shuri through the Sueyoshi Park into the ocean near the Aja port of Naha.

The project started with an extended period of exploration of the park and the river ecosystem, during which the entire Aja river from the spring to the mouth was explored. While walking along the river children experience the change of ecosystems and a variety of different ways of life in and with water and came to understand the complex interdependencies in nature as well as the drastic influence human development has on the environment.

At the end of this exploration the children produced a collage map of the river on which they noted all kinds of observations and information they had gathered.

Aja river and Sueyoshi park Area

While walking along Aja river children experience the change of ecosystems and a variety of different ways of life in and with water.

Finalizing the exploration experience a collagesque map of Aja river, with all kinds of observations and information stuck to it, was created by the children.

One of the exploration tours of the water project focused on the neighborhood of Shuri where we can find many traditional wells. These wells are also sacred places of the Okinawa shamanistic belief system. The children could understand how deeply water and human culture are connected, but also that drying out wells are a big problem and directly related to thoughtless human development.

At the end of the Shizen ni de kara water project stood a two day event with exhibition, workshop and a playground that the children had created themselves (see page 42, 43) and for which they prepared experiments with water for visiting children in whose context they assumed the role of teachers. They also conducted a tour for visitors around the Sueyoshi park, that had been their field for almost one year.

Shizen ni de kara: Exploring Plants

The second year of Shizen ni de kara focused on the topic of plants. Over the course of the year children explored a number of different natural environments in Okinawa, collected various species and finally created their own small illustrated encyclopedia.

The project started with a hands on wood print experience. Children made their own wood print and while carving the stamp experienced the characteristics of wood at first hand. A hand-made sturdy notebook cover from plywood was stamped with the wood print and became the binder for sketches of plants the children produced.

The children were involved in all aspects of the project, from the creation of the notebooks to the definition of the research contents, and were thus able to experience a scientific research process at first hand.

Final presentation of the Shizen ni de kara 2011 project, held in the Sueyoshi park. The self-made Encyclopedia is shown in connection to the environment it was created in and the plants it describes.

Poster of the Shizen ni de kara 2011 project

Shizen ni de kara: Natural Playgrounds

An important aspect of the Shizen ni de kara project was play in the natural environment. From the outset of the project 5 to 6 hours every week were spent playing and just doing whatever seemed fun.

A few simple materials like ropes and knives were taken along but the children used mostly found materials, such as earth, wood, leaves and stones were used to play and to create improvised playgrounds.

It is easy to understand how perception changes being in nature and becomes more open and attentive than in artificial environments.

Cooperative drawing of a playground. Creating such a drawing as a group is an interesting experience that helps develop ideas and furthers dialogue. The drawings below were created to prepare a playground with a tree house for the final event of the Shizen ni de kara 2010 project.

The design of the tree house was worked out with small models. Children selected a tree branch and started experimenting with how to work on such an irregular form and attach a usable space to it.

The making of a tree house. It looks quite dangerous, but if children are properly cautioned they are very careful. Even using all kinds of tools and engaging in all kinds of seemingly dangerous activities we never had a severe injury during our project work. Oddly enough, serious injuries more often seem to happen in apparently safe environments.

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"Creative Learning Environment"

Discovering New Educational Horizons from a small Island

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